

Scientific Guide in Validating CoARA Adjustment Practices

Using Research-in-Research

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Lead beneficiary:	University of Cyprus
Authors:	Zacharias Maniadis (UCY)
Contributor(s):	Sasa Zelenika (UNIRI)
Reviewer(s):	
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1. Current Landscape of Research Assessment at the University of Cyprus

The University of Cyprus (UCY) operates a comprehensive research assessment system that encompasses multiple evaluation mechanisms across different career stages and funding opportunities. This landscape reveals a traditional but robust peer-review-based approach that is well-placed to adjust toward alignment with modern research assessment principles.

1.1 Assessment Types and Scope

UCY conducts research assessment across seven distinct areas. The most significant involves hiring and promoting academic personnel through academic departments, which represents the primary career progression mechanism. Beyond personnel decisions, the Research and Innovation Support Service (RISS) oversees several competitive funding schemes, including internal competitive research grants and the MSCA COFUND postdoctoral program "ONISILOS." The university also evaluates research units and centres, allocates start-up funding for newly hired faculty, provides small annual grants for professional development activities, and administers a Research Excellence Award. This multi-tiered system touches virtually every aspect of academic research life at UCY.

1.2 Current Assessment Methodology

The assessment process relies on peer review conducted by panels comprising both external and internal academics, with decisions passing through four distinct decision-making bodies. A notable characteristic of the current system is the absence of strictly defined quantitative criteria, though such metrics are implicitly utilized by panel members. Quantitative indicators—including publications in 4* journals (as defined by each individual discipline), Q1 journal publications, and h-index scores—exist as unofficial expectations at the department level rather than formal institutional requirements. This informal approach creates flexibility for context adjustment, but also potential inconsistencies across departments and disciplines.

Candidates submit comprehensive documentation including a letter of interest, complete curriculum vitae, a research review with future plans (limited to three pages), a publications list, and up to three representative publications (except for Lecturer positions). Three confidential recommendation letters complete the dossier. Notably absent from current assessment criteria are considerations of Open Science practices and the economic or societal impact of research, though individual panel members may consider these factors at their discretion.

1.3 Rank-Specific Requirements

UCY maintains clear hierarchical expectations for academic advancement. Lecturers require a doctoral degree with demonstrated teaching and research ability. Assistant Professors need at least three years of post-doctoral independent work and original publications in reputable international journals. Associate Professors must accumulate seven years of post-doctoral experience (with four years at university level), demonstrate significant independent research, supervise graduate students, secure research funding, and show evidence of international recognition through citations, invited presentations, and editorial roles. Full Professors require eleven years of post-doctoral experience, international recognition, significant teaching and administrative contributions, successful supervision of doctoral students, and advancement of

the university's mission. Most of these requirements are not quantified, but left to the discretion of the panels/departments.

1.4 Transition Toward Reform

UCY is a signatory of ARRA and has elaborated a CoARA Action Plan which is to be soon approved from the relevant institutional bodies. UCY has initiated steps to align with CoARA principles. The university appointed RISS as the monitoring entity for CoARA implementation and designated the SInnoPSis ERA Chair research unit to evaluate practices using evidence-based approaches and state-of-the-art research on research assessment. Much of this reform work will occur through EU-funded projects including TWIN4MERIT, SInnoPSis, SECURE, OPUS, OSCAR and YUFE2030, coordinated or supported by RISS.

This transition represents a shift from traditional, metrics-implicit evaluation toward one that incorporates broader considerations of research quality, societal impact, and open science practices. However, the current landscape reveals a system still largely rooted in conventional peer review with informal quantitative benchmarks.

2. University of Cyprus CoARA Action Plan 2025-2028

The University of Cyprus (UCY) has developed a comprehensive Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) Action Plan as part of the CoARA Boost Teaming project OSCAR (Open Science Collaboration for Research Career Advancement and Policy Innovation), co-funded by Horizon Europe. This ambitious reform initiative, developed in collaboration with the University of Rijeka, Croatia, and the European Office of Cyprus, aims to transform how research and researchers are assessed, recognized, and supported at the institution.

The plan emerges from growing recognition that traditional metrics and rankings fail to capture the full breadth and value of research activity. As a CoARA signatory since May 2023, UCY is committed to establishing a research culture that is open, responsible, inclusive, and supportive of diverse research contributions. The CoARA Action Plan spans the 2025-2028 period and represents both an institutional transformation and an ambition to serve as a national model for reform.

2.1 Strategic Vision and Objectives

UCY's research assessment vision centres on five overarching strategic objectives: developing inclusive and context-sensitive frameworks for researcher evaluation; aligning research careers with principles of transparency, diversity, and openness; enhancing capacity building through training and participation in the CoARA network; institutionalizing Open Science practices within all assessment procedures; and influencing broader national policy change through strategic engagement with authorities.

These objectives reflect UCY's commitment to CoARA's core principles, particularly concerning the recognition of research diversity, qualitative evaluation, and responsible metrics use. The plan places particular emphasis on integrating Open Science principles, developing qualitative and contextual evaluation frameworks, and promoting equity across all research career stages.

2.2 Institutional Readiness

UCY enters this reform process with substantial advantages. As a research-intensive institution and member of the Young Universities for the Future of Europe (YUFE) alliance, UCY has demonstrated consistent growth and progressive orientation toward responsible research and innovation. The Research and Innovation Support Service (RISS) serves as the central coordination hub, while the SInnoPSis research group on research-on-research adds methodological rigor by applying empirical techniques to inform assessment practices.

An ongoing internal mapping exercise conducted in preparation reveals both institutional strengths and improvement areas, particularly the need for consistent approaches to evaluating diverse research contributions and more systematic support for early-career researchers. UCY's Centres of Excellence, such as the KIOS Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence in Information and Communication Technologies, exemplify the interdisciplinary research and societal collaboration that the new assessment framework aims to recognize and further reward.

2.3 UCY CoARA Action Categories and Key Initiatives

The UCY CoARA Action Plan (AP) organizes 19 proposed actions into six strategic categories. The Careers/Researchers category focuses on supporting researchers through transparent career

pathways, including mapping academic staff to R1-R4 career stages and developing cross-sectoral career progression frameworks. The Assessment category tackles evaluation reform through narrative-based CVs, updated recruitment and promotion criteria, and pilot programs for internal funding schemes and research unit evaluations.

Training initiatives include Open Science sessions covering open access, open data, legal frameworks, reproducibility, and citizen engagement. The Governance category establishes support structures, notably the creation of an Open Science Committee and development of a Responsible Research and Research Assessment Policy. Feedback/Monitoring mechanisms ensure iterative development through surveys, stakeholder consultations, and implementation tracking. Finally, National Policy/Engagement actions position UCY as a national leader through workshops, advocacy, and participation in CoARA working groups.

Critical early actions include mapping staff to career stages, conducting readiness assessments, consideration of how official criteria should be updated, and launching Open Science training—all scheduled for 2025. Medium-term initiatives focus on piloting new evaluation guides and conducting research on assessment practices, while long-term actions emphasize cross-sectoral career development and contributions to CoARA working groups.

2.4 Implementation of the UCY CoARA AP and Stakeholder Engagement

Implementation of the UCY CoARA AP employs a participatory approach led by RISS with oversight from the Vice Rector of Academic Affairs. Actions are organized into short-term (2025), medium-term (2026-2027), and long-term (2028) initiatives with clear timelines, responsibilities, and dependencies. Each action includes measurable indicators tracked through digital dashboards and centralized data collection systems.

In this framework and generally in its operation, UCY adopts a Quadruple Helix stakeholder engagement model encompassing academia, government, civil society, and entrepreneurship. Academic engagement includes departmental forums, co-creation workshops, and cross-institutional partnerships through the CoARA National Chapter Cyprus. Government collaboration involves strategic dialogue with the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy and EU institutions. Civil society participation ensures societal relevance, while entrepreneurial stakeholders help align assessment with innovation and knowledge transfer.

2.5 Monitoring, Challenges, and Mitigation of the UCY CoARA AP Execution

The monitoring framework combines quantitative completion tracking with qualitative outcomes assessment, including researcher satisfaction and narrative CV adoption. SInnoPSis will conduct periodic evaluations, with results feeding into annual implementation reports shared with governance bodies and external stakeholders.

Internal challenges include resistance to change among senior staff, disciplinary variability in expectations, early-career researcher concerns, and peer review workload increase. Mitigation strategies include awareness campaigns, inclusive design processes, dedicated ECR support, and structured peer review systems. External challenges involve potential misalignment with national policies, sectoral engagement gaps, and resource constraints, addressed through policy advocacy, expanded stakeholder involvement, and targeted funding proposals.

3. Meta-Research Principles Guiding the Plan Implementation

An analysis from the perspective of meta-research (the study of research itself) can substantially help with the continual refinement, evaluation and implementation of UCY's CoARA Action Plan, facilitating its ultimate success.

3.1 Empirical Evidence on Reform Effectiveness

The implementation of the plan should carefully draw from the empirical evidence on designing and implementing assessment reforms actually *work*. Meta-research has shown that many well-intentioned interventions in science can have unintended consequences or fail to achieve their stated goals. To avoid these pitfalls, the AP should carefully utilise existing evidence on:

- Conditions under which narrative CVs improve evaluation quality (vs. simply shifting biases).
- Factors facilitating the success of qualitative assessment in reducing gaming behaviours (rather than merely transforming them).
- The causal effects of different assessment criteria are on researcher behaviour.

3.2 Acknowledge Challenges in Operationalising the Measurement of Key Concepts

The AP emphasizes moving beyond traditional metrics to assess research "quality," "societal impact," and "diverse contributions," but providing operational definitions of these concepts is challenging. Meta-research demonstrates that:

- Quality is multidimensional, context-dependent, and often subjective (Tennant and Ross-Hellauer, 2020)
- Peer judgment, while valuable, is subject to numerous biases (prestige bias, Matthew effects, demographic biases, e.g. see Li et al., 2013) - of course, this is weakness partly shared by quantitative metrics, which simply summarise peer-reviewed literature.
- There are trade-offs between the objectives of transparency and objectivity and being misuse-free. New qualitative indicators can become new metrics that are gamed in different ways (Biagioli, 2020).

3.3 Validation for new Indicators

New assessment frameworks and indicators, proposed by the AP need to be validated against meaningful outcomes. What constitutes a "good" research assessment? Desirable attributes of good assessment systems are scientifically measurable: validity, reliability (inter-rater and intertemporal), transparency, fairness and cost-efficiency. The implementation of the plan should include precise forms of data acquisition to perform this validation. For instance, rigorous faculty surveys should be used to examine transparency, fairness and cost efficiency, while data on evaluators' attributes and assigned scores to candidates will be needed to assess reliability. Gathering the latter type of data will have to address confidentiality issues. A key issue is whether training evaluators on "responsible assessment" improves consistent or unbiased assessment.

3.4 Goodhart's Law

"When a measure becomes a target, it ceases to be a good measure." The AP aims to complement traditional metrics with new criteria (Open Science practices, narrative CVs, societal impact), but these too will become targets that researchers optimize for. Theoretical meta-science analysis (utilising mathematical models and simulations) will be needed in later stages to perform deeper analysis and examine:

- How to prevent gaming of new "responsible" indicators.
- What behaviours might be inadvertently discouraged (e.g., high-risk research that may not demonstrate immediate societal impact).
- How to maintain the informational value of indicators once they become high-stakes.
- Equilibrium Effects: Researchers respond strategically to incentive systems. We need to model how researchers might adapt their behaviour when multiple reforms are implemented simultaneously. For example, if narrative CVs become standard but hiring committees still face cognitive limitations and time constraints, they may develop new heuristics that reintroduce the problems the reform aimed to solve.

It should be noted that such models take year to build, and thus they should be viewed as a long-run and continually evolving project for UCY SInnoPSis.

3.5 One-Size-Fits-All Risk

The implementation of the AP needs to carefully consider disciplinary variability and avoid proposing uniform solutions across fields. Meta-research shows that research practices, output types, collaboration patterns, and impact pathways vary dramatically across disciplines (e.g. Olejniczak et al., 2022, Maniadis, 2025). What counts as "quality" or "impact" differs fundamentally between, say, theoretical mathematics and public health research. The implementation of the AP needs to study disciplinary differences empirically – using surveys - to avoid systematically advantaging or disadvantaging certain research areas, or serve as a time-consuming but pointless box-ticking exercise.

3.6 Short-Term vs. Long-Term Outcomes

The 2025-2028 timeline may be insufficient to observe meaningful effects on research quality or career outcomes. Early-career researchers entering under the new system may face different opportunities and constraints than established researchers. The implementation of the AP needs to consider fairness across cohorts or how to study differential effects by career stage.

4. Recommendations

4.1 Recommendations from a Meta-Research Perspective

To address these challenges, the realization of UCY's AP could consider:

1. **Incorporate experimental or quasi-experimental designs** where feasible (e.g., randomizing order of reform implementation across departments, using matched control groups). Acknowledging the institutional challenges in approving and implementing such an approach, this can be viewed as a long-run target.
2. **Develop or adopt validated measurement instruments** for key constructs like "assessment quality" and "researcher wellbeing". This can be achieved with the collaboration psychometric experts affiliated with SInnoPSis.
3. **Plan for long-term follow-up** beyond the initial 2025-2028 period to capture delayed effects.
4. **Conduct systematic reviews** of existing evidence on assessment reforms before finalizing interventions. This can be undertaken by SInnoPSis experts, provided sufficient future funding to ensure the long-run presence of the SInnoPSis research group.
5. **Model potential unintended consequences** and include monitoring for gaming behaviours. This can also be undertaken by SInnoPSis experts, as specified above.
6. **Share data openly** (where ethically appropriate) to enable external validation and meta-analysis
7. **Provide feedback** about the generated evidence back to CoARA to help them reflect on their own practices.

4.2 Recommendations from a Policy Perspective

1. **Prepare an action plan for the utilization of AI tools at UCY** for reducing the cost of peer review in research assessment. Such tools have remarkable promise, in many dimensions, which include: - Automatically identifying and cataloguing different types of research outputs - Analysing citations and mentions in regional publications, policy documents, local media and non-academic sources - Automatically populating researcher profiles from open infrastructures - Generating initial drafts of narrative CVs based on structured data. Of course, the validity and replicability of these tools should be also established. Piloting such tools may require successful external funding, and validation should take place in the medium term. Such funding and validation could take place within YUFE and other coalitions where UCY is a member.
2. **Develop a set of principles and structured tools for research assessment**, with the aim of sharing it with local policymakers for the purpose of assessing local research institutions. This is a topical challenge for the Cypriot research ecosystem with a fast-growing university sector and much potential for abuse of quantitative indicators.
3. **Provide rigorous training on responsible research to local institutions** crucial for the implementation of assessment, especially judges and policymakers. The judicial decisions frequently affect the de facto practices of local universities, and they should be

based on a solid understanding on research assessment. Similarly, policymakers should have a basic understanding of holistic assessment and the pitfalls of fostering a shallow quantitative approach.

4. **Utilize the hub NOUS (kNOWLEDge hUb of Strovolos)** to engage with the public and policymakers with science cafes and discussions of topics such trust in science and conspiracy theories, the credibility of research, etc.
5. **Develop seminars and modules** to promote best research practices among UCY colleagues. For instance, providing evidence on the increasing role of pre-publication computational replication, to motivate researchers to accelerate the publication process by following careful and transparent replication packages. In fact, pre-publication replication is becoming the norm in top journal in many disciplines. Another objective is to provide state-of-the-art guidance in research documentation and transparency.
6. **Prepare a plan for the commercial** exploitation of the automatic UCY AI tools for use by other institutions for their own research assessment.

5. UCY as a Meta-Research Hub for Evidence-Based Research Assessment Reform

5.1 Positioning UCY as a Capacity-Building Reference Point

The University of Cyprus (UCY) is uniquely positioned to serve as a European hub for evidence-based research assessment reform through its distinctive integration of the SInnoPSis ERA Chair research unit within its CoARA implementation framework. Unlike institutions that approach assessment reform primarily as an administrative or policy exercise, UCY embeds rigorous meta-research methodology directly into its reform process. This creates a replicable model where research-on-research expertise systematically validates reform interventions, monitors unintended consequences, and generates generalizable knowledge about what actually works in changing assessment culture. UCY's commitment to open data sharing and external validation enables the broader research community to learn from both its successes and failures.

UCY's capacity-building value extends beyond its own institutional boundaries through several mechanisms. First, SInnoPSis brings state-of-the-art expertise in analysing how assessment systems shape researcher behaviour, detecting gaming of indicators, and measuring research quality across diverse disciplines. Second, UCY's participation in multiple EU initiatives (TWIN4MERIT, YUFE2030, OSCAR, SECURE, OPUS, iRISE) positions it as a knowledge broker connecting European reform efforts.

Importantly, SInnoPSis also closely collaborates with key meta-research centres in Europe (e.g., QUEST centre at Charite, Berlin, and EXCELSIOR Chair in Coimbra, Portugal). Close scientific collaboration with these centres will allow SInnoPSis to develop concrete methodologies, as well as maintain and enhance its research team, building on European projects. This will ensure the sustainability and long-run institutionalization of research-in-research at UCY, and its impact upon its network of collaborators in YERUN, YUFE, etc., as a model to be emulated. In turn, these alliances can help SInnoPSis validate its scientific approaches, keep its research personnel, and facilitate its long-run status at UCY.

5.2 Teaming with the University of Rijeka: A Meta-Research Partnership

The OSCAR project's teaming between UCY and UNIRI creates exceptional opportunities for mutual learning and methodological advancement. UCY's meta-research validation framework can be systematically adapted to evaluate UNIRI's research assessment practices, strengthening both institutions while demonstrating the scalability of evidence-based reform.

UNIRI brings complementary strengths to this partnership. As Croatia's first university to adopt an Open Science Declaration (2019) and having successfully implemented targeted interventions through the OPUS project with early-career researchers, UNIRI has practical experience in culture change. The teaming allows UCY to test whether its meta-research protocols can be successfully transferred across different national contexts, institutional histories, and research ecosystems—a critical validation of the approach's generalizability.

The meta-research methodology developed at UCY could inform UNIRI's evaluation in three specific ways: First, by applying the same validated measurement instruments to assess "assessment quality" and researcher wellbeing at both institutions, enabling direct comparisons. Second, by implementing quasi-experimental designs where UNIRI serves as a comparison case

for specific UCY interventions, strengthening causal inference. Third, by jointly developing field-specific assessment criteria that account for disciplinary differences across both institutions' research portfolios. As per WP5 of OSCAR, further online meetings will be held in November and December 2025 between the two partners, to enhance and facilitate the adoption of the research-in-research perspective, methodologies and concrete proposals at UNIRI.

5.3 Preparation Protocol for Receiving Organizations

Before engagement, the receiving institution should:

- Conduct baseline mapping of current assessment practices, including implicit criteria actually used versus official policies, documented with interviews and policy analysis.
- Establish internal working group comprising research administrators, early-career researchers, senior faculty, and if available, staff with social science research methods expertise.
- Compile institutional data on researcher demographics (R1-R4 career stages), current assessment outcomes (promotion rates, funding success), and any existing researcher satisfaction surveys.
- Identify champion stakeholders at multiple levels (department heads, vice-rectors, influential researchers) who will advocate for evidence-based reform.

This systematic preparation ensures that guidance from the advanced partner translates into actionable institutional change grounded in local context while maintaining methodological rigor.

6. Conclusions

UCY's CoARA Action Plan is ambitious and well-intentioned. To truly serve as a model for others and contribute to the science of research assessment, the implementation of the AP needs to apply meta-scientific principles and empirical rigor. The involvement of SIInnoPSis may provide the methodological attention needed to ensure that the action plan generates reliable, generalizable knowledge about what works in research assessment reform. Sustainability and enhancement of the SIInnoPSis group is a prerequisite for this. Its impact at the European level is evidenced by its fruitful participation to relevant scientific CoARA action groups. Ultimately, based on the capacity-building stemming from SIInnoPSis, YUFE, OSCAR, YERUN and the related activities, UCY is in a position to serve as a European hub for evidence-based research assessment reforms.

Appendix: Research Assessment at UCY

A. Types of Assessment at UCY

1. Hiring and promoting academic personnel (Academic departments).
2. Internal Competitive Research Grants (RISS).
3. MSCA COFUND Postdoctoral Researchers funding Scheme “ONISILOS” (RISS).
4. Research Units and Centres (Research Committee - RISS).
5. Start-up funding for newly hired faculty members (Research Committee).
6. Small annual research grant for travelling, conferences, publications etc. (Research Committee – RISS).
7. Research Excellence Award (Research Committee - RISS).

B. PROCESS AND CRITERIA

Research assessment takes place through a peer review process of a panel of external and internal academics. The decision passes through 4 distinct decision-making bodies.

Quantitative criteria not strictly defined but implied at some positions. Quantitative indicators utilised by panel members explicitly or implicitly. Quantitative criteria are defined unofficially at the level of expectations of the department level (4* Journal Publications, Q1 Journal publications, h-index, etc.).

Open Science, economic and societal impact of research currently not included in the assessment criteria, at the discretion of panel members to consider them

MATERIAL THAT IS ASKED

- Letter of interest and complete Curriculum Vitae.
- Review of research work and a brief description of future scientific plans (up to 3 pages).
- List of publications, representative publications (up to 3 publications, each to be submitted as a separate file). Not required for the rank of Lecturer.
- Three confidential letters of recommendation.

C. WHAT IS EXPECTED FOR EACH RANK

For the position of Lecturer, a doctoral degree from a recognized university is required, as well as evidence of ability in university teaching and research.

For the position of Assistant Professor, the qualifications for the Lecturer position are required, in addition to at least three years of independent university teaching or research work after obtaining the doctoral degree, at a recognized university or research centre.

Original publications in reputable international scientific journals or other publications of recognized value that indicate a significant contribution to science are also required.

For the position of Associate Professor, the qualifications for the Assistant Professor position are required, along with the following additional qualifications:

- (a) At least seven years of total university or equivalent work after obtaining the doctoral degree, of which at least four must be university-level work, or holding a position at a corresponding rank at a recognized university.
- (b) Publication of works, such as articles in reputable international scientific journals or monographs or books from recognized publishers, that demonstrate significant independent research work.
- (c) The ability to supervise and promote research, which includes overseeing postgraduate students, leading or contributing significantly to research programs, or securing funding for research activities.
- (d) Evidence of international recognition of the candidate's contribution to a specific research field, such as research citations, invitations for scientific presentations, requests for article reviews, research proposals, or doctoral dissertations, participation in editorial boards of scientific journals, or involvement in organizing conferences.

For the position of Professor, the qualifications required for the Associate Professor position are needed, along with the following additional qualifications:

- (a) At least eleven years of total university or equivalent work after obtaining the doctoral degree, of which at least four must be university-level work, or holding a position at the rank of Professor at a recognized university.
- (b) International recognition of scientific work.
- (c) Significant contribution to the teaching and administrative work of the university.
- (d) Supervision and successful completion of research programs or doctoral dissertations.
- (e) Contribution to the advancement of the university's teaching and administrative work.

D. STEPS FOR ADJUSTING TO COARA PRINCIPLES SO FAR

- Appointed the Research and Innovation Support Service (RISS) as the competent entity of the University to monitor the implementation of the CoARA provisions and to report to the Research Committee. Most of the actions needed will take place mainly **through TWIN4MERIT & SInnoPSis**, YUFE2030 and other EU funded projects that RISS is coordinating /participating.
- Appointed the SInnoPSis (ERA Chair) research unit as the responsible entity to evaluate practices, criteria and tools at the university based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

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